

LINGUISTIC PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION FROM ENGLISH TO UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the problem of translating literary text. The article analyzes the features of translating literary texts, and also it demonstrates ways of solving linguistic problems and types of translating problems which occurs in the process of translating from English to Uzbek.

Introduction

The early theorists of translation were primarily translators themselves, and they tried to create preliminary theories based on their own experiences and those of their colleagues. From ancient times until now, the issue of creating a translation as if it were the original has been the cause of wide discussions. The early translators thought that copying the literature directly was the right way, mainly because the ancient scriptures were all copied and the translators saw this as a model. This, of course, caused the translation to become unclear or incomprehensible. To this end, later, some translators began to create theories about the need to repeat the general meaning of the translated work rather than literal translation, and it wouldn't be exaggeration to say that this issue is one of the most important problems of today. "The practice of translation has appeared, and the question of how to translate the original into the native language, word for word or freely, is considered a problem facing translators" ¹.

Some of the creators working in the field of translation work in this field in favor of word-for-word translation, while some of them chose free translation and created many translated works on this basis. First of all, it is not important which type of translation is chosen the most important thing is translator must create a kind of text which is based on not copying comma and full stops, words, or length of the story but meaning, he or she must explain the story clearly and easily to the reader as original one .

The main reason for such differences was that the translators neglected such important factors as the type of the text being translated, the purpose of the translation, and the taste of the reader. As a result, a number of types of translation were formed, we will consider them one by one below:

1. Creative translation - in this type of translation, the original linguistic means, their textual meanings and stylistic functions are recreated in harmony with the grammar rules of the common language.

2. Word-to-word translation - in this type of translation, important elements such as word combinations, stable phrases, grammatical structure, word order in the translated text are not subject to and adapted to the standard rules of the language being translated. It is translated according to the dictionary meaning of z. As a result, the created work becomes a simple text consisting of a collection of words, which has lost its original emotional, spiritual, national, historical, and period aspects. That is why literal translation has been condemned until now. As an example, many critical opinions have been expressed about it. As an example, A. Sharif in his lectures considered word-for-word translation to be a "bad method", and T. Gnedich said that it is not a creative work, but "a circus performance". X. noted that it is a similar prank.

3. Free translation - in this type of translation, the translator, ignoring the form of the translation, narrated the content of the text in his own words. Almost no attempt has been made to recreate the tasks of visual media. Gudrat Musayev in his work entitled "Theories of Translation Theory" describes such a translation as follows: "Emotional expressions created by the author with a dense image fall to the level of a lightless statement."

4. Figurative translation - in this type of translation, the linguistic means that create an image typical of individual creativity are replaced by unreasonable figurative expressions, words that express feelings, and lofty combinations. As a result, the norm of the author's image is broken, and a text with a different style is created, contrary to the scope. That's probably what it means to raise an eyebrow (Gudrat Musayev, the basics of translation theory FAN pages 25-26)

5. Adaptive translation - in this type of translation, the original is treated very liberally.

It is true that the subject of the translated text, the composition of the characters, and the content are preserved, but in the work, the traditions, mental and emotional states, nationality, and the same features of the language being translated are mixed with the same features of the translated work. to make it more clear and clear to the reader.

6. Authored translation - Such a translation is a translation made with the consent of the author. The author, realizing that his work does not have a high artistic aesthetic value, hands it over to another translator who he thinks has better skills than him, and wants the work to be translated as soon as possible. As a result, the translator shortens, removes or adds some parts of the work. 'satisfied. As a result, a new work is born, if the reader is familiar with the original and the translated copy of the work, he will come to the conclusion that there are 2 different works covering the same topic.

We have discussed above the types of translation and the problems of translation encountered in them, and the first problem facing future translators is not only their ability to choose the right type of translation from English to Uzbek, but also to overcome the problems they encounter. Nowadays, translation from English through an intermediary language is becoming a habit in our country. All scholars have different opinions about this, including Chukovsky, in his article entitled "Third God of Art", he writes that he is completely against this method and describes such translation as "nonsense, useless work", our famous writer

Abdulla Qahhor In his article entitled "Concerns of translation studies", he opposes the opinion of the critic and defends the method of indirect translation.

He writes that we should always respect translators who translate directly, but that such translators are few, so why should we give up on the opportunity to translate a work written in a foreign language from Russian.

In our opinion, both of the issues raised are valid. On the one hand, Chukovsky was right, because no matter how many difficulties and hardships the author brings to the world, someone easily distorts or changes its meaning and conveys it to the reader, it certainly weighs on the author. Therefore, if in indirect translation the work is translated from the original by a skilled translator, then it is correct to translate this work into another language, but if it is the opposite, then the artistic aesthetic color and meaning of the work will be completely changed. and it can damage the authenticity of the century. Considering these aspects, Chukovsky is completely right. But we cannot say that our writer Abdullah Qahhor is unfair either, because when will we really destroy this nation's customs and culture, We cannot waste time waiting for a skilled translator who understands the language to come and translate for us. If we have good talents, we should use them. Until our direct translators mature. Examples of works translated from English to Uzbek language: Viyninch's novel "Suna", Shakespeare's "King Lear", "Romeo and Juliet", "Othello", "Hamlet", "Julius Caesar". In addition, in one of his lectures, A. Sharif considered the practice of word-for-word translation to be a bad method, while T. Grendich said that it is not a creative work, but a "circus spectacle". describes. According to Kh. Khantemirova, "The best word-for-word translation" also says that it is unable to fully interpret the richness and originality of the original. In our opinion, the scientists were right, because translating the words that appear in the context only according to the meaning in the dictionary can definitely damage the naturalness, nationality and beauty of the work.

One of the problems that arise in the process of translation from English to Uzbek is the problem of the translator's choice of lexical units, that is, the translator finds and replaces the lexical units given in the original text with the same meaningful units from English to Uzbek. Of course, finding the original meaning of the word given in the work before replacing it is the first thing, because even the most perfect dictionaries only give the meanings used in the literary language. it can be said that there are almost no dictionaries that fully cover the spoken and literary meanings in different dialects. Even if it is given, the translator should find the most appropriate one of these meanings, if not, then he should be able to feel the meaning of this word based on the situation in the text. All languages, including English, have national cultural characteristics, so sometimes the linguistic units used to translate an idea may not correspond to the equivalent given in the dictionary. Well, how should the translator act in such a situation is one of the problems of translation. The semantic features of English and Uzbek languages, the use of words, their ability to combine with other words, due to their different positions in the lexical system, do not always correspond to each other, and all cases of differences in meaning and it is impossible to cover completely, that's why we classify the types of word compatibility in English and Uzbek languages as follows:

a) full lexical compatibility- we can see this type rarely in Uzbek and English language and this belongs to these lexical groups: geographical names, proper names, scientific and technical terms, month, week, days and numbers.

b) Partial lexical compatibility - in the process of translation, partial compatibility of the meaning of words is a common situation. There are many polysemantic words in the language, which do not always fully correspond to each other, for example: eye (the eye of a tree, the eye of a stream, etc.), and in English, head (head, director, head of state, etc.). The translator should be able to find and reveal the meaning of the same word from the context. Or we know that some words have a synonymous line, and although these synonyms are the same in terms of meaning, they differ from each other stylistically, in terms of the place of use, formal or informal, oral, bookish.

c) Inconsistency in general - the state of inconsistency in general is more noticeable in the process of translating specific words. Words that do not have a lexical alternative: typical words used in everyday life (cradle, blanket, underwear, hat, etc.); nicknames and geographical place names (Anora, Maftuna, Navbahor, Khatirchi, etc.); greetings and greetings, units of weight and length.

We have mentioned above that one of the problems encountered in the process of translation from English to our mother tongue is the translation of special words. Special words are national words that embody the culture of the nation and have no equivalent in other languages, which can be understood only by representatives of that nation. Such words are also prevented from being translated due to lack of equivalents. "The difference between languages is usually explained by the fact that certain concepts, events, and customs that exist in the material life of one people do not occur in the way of life of another people, and because of this, they are not naturally present in the same people's language. In addition, some pairs of two languages that are in a relationship of lexical equivalence may differ from each other in some features. This situation hinders their exchange in translation while determining the national character of language units. In the process of translating special words, we may encounter two types of difficulties:

1. Non-existence of an exact equivalent for the original language words
2. The difficulty of fully expressing the specific words of the original language, the national, historical, cultural, color of this people in the translated language.

We discussed the lexical problems of translation from English to Uzbek above, now we want to talk about grammatical problems below. One of the main reasons for the occurrence of grammatical problems is that English and our mother tongue belong to different language families and language groups. Morphologically, they belong to two different types, the English language is morphologically synthetic in terms of analytical writing, and the Uzbek language belongs to the agglutinative group.

In the process of translating complex sentences in English, the word order does not always match, and the position of the preposition and the postposition may change.

Difficulties in translation of phrasal units: It is no exaggeration to say that it is one of the most painful problems. Translation of phraseological units, which are considered more complex than lexical units of the language, is not only very important and complex, but also one of the most responsible problems of translation ¹. The main reason for this is that

phraseological units perform more different methodological tasks than in the simple statement of oral and written speech or thought, that is, they polish, color, and increase the impact of our thoughts, so they are interpreted loosely in translation. It is equivalent to recreating the figurative and emotional value of the artistic work being translated. The translation of phraseological units is very complicated, and the main reason for this is as follows:

- Phrases have a complex structure both lexically and semantically.
- In addition, the fact that the phraseologisms have a national cultural character creates difficulties for the translators.

Many phraseologisms are not always used in their meaning and are sometimes used in artistic speech in such a way that their form and content have changed, and this situation imposes an additional stylistic task on them. As a result, such cases make the translation process even more complicated.

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